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SIMULATION OF PARALLEL KINEMATIC MACHINE WITH SPECIFIC SOLUTIONS OF THE PASSIVE TRANSLATORY JOINT

Saša Živanović¹, Ljubomir Nešovanović², Zoran Dimić³, Radovan Puzović⁴

Abstract: The paper discusses ideas for the development of new 3-axis parallel kinematic machines, which have one dominant elongated axis, with the application of specific solutions for a passive translatory joint, which uses mechanisms that generate a straight line, such as the Chebyshev's mechanism.

Key words: Chebyshev's mechanism, parallel kinematic machine, machine simulation

1 INTRODUCTION

The development of new concepts of parallel kinematic machines is still a research challenge. The challenge for the realization of machine tool structures with superior performance and low price compared to conventional machines is current. So far, a large number of machines with parallel kinematics of different topologies with 3-6 degrees of freedom have been developed.

Given that five-axis machining is not necessary for the majority of the machining that is carried out, the focus of research are 3-axis PKM [1], and hybrid kinematic machine tools [2].

In this paper, one class of 3-axis parallel mechanisms is considered, with translatory movable actuators and a specific solution of a passive translatory-rotating joint based on the Chebyshev's mechanism [3,4]. The paper gives an overview of the considered machines with elongating one axis, with a description and simulation of the kinematics of their mechanisms.

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2 PARALLEL KINEMATIC MACHINE WITH ELONGATING ONE AXIS

The Hexaglide and Triaglide mechanisms are examples where the working space is elongated along one axis, as the main axis of movement, which is otherwise a common feature of machines with a serial structure. Based on the importance of that one axis as dominant, a new spatial parallel mechanisms with 3 degrees of freedom was considered for horizontal and vertical machines tools.

The paper considers a class of similar 3-axis mechanisms with parallel kinematics, which have an elongated dominant axis, and parallel guides. The mechanisms have specific solution for translatory rotary joint. Due to the use of parallel guides, there is a possibility of elongating one axis of the workspace, as the dominant axis of movement. In addition, the structure of the mechanism, dimensions and movements of the moving platform allow the installation of two serial axes, that is, the construction of hybrid kinematic five-axis machines.

2.1 Initial parallel mechanism pn101

The CAD model of the initial mechanism [1] is shown in Fig.1. As can be seen, the mechanism consists of a moving platform, three articulated parallelograms c1, c2 and c3 and a stationary base on which there are two parallel guides. Two crossed articulated parallelograms c1 and c2, with spherical and/or universal i.e. gimbal joints, are attached to the moving platform by one of their ends, while at the other end they are ends connected to independent sliders s1 and s2, which with one common guide on the base form two reinforced and controlled translation joints.

Figure 1. *Initial parallel mechanism pn101*

The third articulated parallelogram c3 is at one end, over the passive translatory-rotary joints with 2 degrees of freedom, attached to the moving platform, while its other end is attached to the slider s3 by its rotary joints, which with the guide on the base forms the third reinforced and controlled translatory joint. By moving the sliders s1, s2 and s3, 3 degrees of freedom of the moving platform or the tool are provided so that the platform remains parallel to itself when moving in space, i.e. keeps constant orientation in space.

2.2 Chebyshev's mechanism

The Chebyshev mechanism is quite simple in construction, and belongs to the group of mechanisms that have the possibility to generate a straight line. The point P of the moving joint CD describes an approximately straight line. The geometric proportions of the mechanism segments are given in Fig.2.

Figure 2. *Chebyshev's mechanism*

Mechanism kinematics simulation is a standard option of CAD/CAM system. This simple design of Chebyshev's linkage is modeled in CAD/CAM system and simulated in module Mechanism. The simulation procedure includes: (i) modeling of the mechanism segments, (ii) defining the kinematic connections (Pin), (iii) defining the servomotor, (iv) defining the analysis for the simulation and (v) starting the simulation and drawing the trace of the desired point (P). The option for drawing a trace of movement for moving elements in the assembly (Trace Curves) is used. After simulation, result on Fig.3 shows that a straight line is generated by moving the P point of Chebyshev's linkage.

Figure 3. *Chebyshev's mechanism simulation*

The idea is to use the ability to move the given point P along a straight line as a passive translational joint of the parallel kinematic machine, which will contain a pair of coupled Chebyshev mechanisms.

2.3 Parallel mechanism P2 Glide

Parallel mechanism P2 Glide was derived from the parallel mechanism pn101 [1]. The difference compared to the initial pn101 mechanism is the replacement of the passive translatory rotary joint with the Chebyshev's mechanism. Figure 4 shows conceptions of P2-glide machines with one elongated axis and a passive translatory joint based on the Chebyshev's mechanism in vertical (Fig.4a) and horizontal (Fig.4b) configuration. For both conceptions of the machine, two guides are used, which in both cases are horizontal.

Figure 4. *Conceptions of P2 Glide machines with one elongated axis and a passive translatory joint based on the Chebyshev's mechanism*

2.4 Parallel mechanism P3 Glide

Parallel mechanism P3 Glide is a novel parallel mechanism [5,6] which, unlike the previously considered mechanisms, has a stationary base on which there are three parallel guides. The parallel mechanism itself is similar to the previous one and also uses the passive translatory rotary joint with Chebyshev's mechanism, Fig.5. In the case of the P3 Glide machine, horizontal (Fig.5a) and vertical (Fig.5b) concepts are also considered. Unlike the previous machine concept (P2 Glide), in the case of the P3 Glide machine, three guides are used, which are horizontal for the vertical variant of the machine, and vertical for the horizontal variant of the machine.

Figure 5. *Conceptions of P3 Glide machines with one elongated axis and a passive translatory joint based on the Chebyshev's mechanism*

3 SIMULATION OF PARALLEL KINEMATIC MACHINE WITH ELONGATING ONE AXIS

The simulation of the kinematics of each new mechanism that is include into the structure of the machine tool is very important in the development phase of new configuration. This kind of simulation implies the possibility of modeling a parallel mechanism with all kinematic connections between components, which give the possibility of movement of the elements of the virtual prototype as a system of rigid bodies. This type of simulation was considered during the development of another mechanism with hybrid kinematics, which was presented in [7].

Figure 6, shows conceptual model of P2 glide mechanism in vertical configuration with defined kinematic links of the parallel mechanism in the Mechanism module of the PTC Creo 9.0 CAD/CAM system. The paper shows the simulation of the mechanism from Fig. 4a, and it can be realized for the other shown conceptions and variants of the machine.

Figure 6. *Defined kinematic links of the parallel mechanism in the Mechanism module of the PTC Creo 9.0 CAD/CAM system*

Figure 6, shows the all kinemtic joints and characteristic marks with their schematic representation and name of the joint. For this mechanism used appropriate standard kinematic connections, such as Pin, Slider and Ball were used. They are also for simulation purposes used possibilities of defining motor as the driving element, and plotting the trace of the point on observed assembly during movement (Trace Curves). Such assembly formation it allows moving the model within the bounds defined by the joints, which is special importance for noticing possible collisions during movement of mechanism elements. This simulation will also affect the final design of individual components of the machine, given that only a simplified conceptual model is considered here.

The simulation of kinematics in the Mechanism module was realized on an example of machining a test workpiece for machine tools.

This includes motion simulations with linear and circular interpolation. In addition to movement, simulation results were monitored for individual joints with a graphical representation of the desired dependencies. Part of those results for an example of circular interpolation is shown in Fig. 7. For the considered mechanism from Fig. 6, drives for the movement of the tool tip by circular interpolation are defined for finishing of the cylindrical part on the test workpiece. Different reports (Measure Results) can be created after to the completed simulation. The dependences of the change of the coordinates X, Y and Z as a function of time for the movement of the programmed point of the tool tip, and the dependences of the changes of the drive translatory axes for achieving circular interpolation, are shown on Fig.7.

Figure 7. Simulation of parallel mechanism kinematics in the Mechanism module

4 CONCLUSION

Based on of the conducted research, a number of conclusions were drawn related to the planned development of new concepts of parallel kinematic machines. The possibility of applying simplified virtual conceptions in the initial phase of the development of new mechanisms where kinematic simulation of the mechanism has a very important role is also shown.

The presented simulation model showed the importance of further optimizing the appearance of the moving platform and machine moving components in order to enable the full potential of the rotary and spherical joints, and at the same time maximize the working space of the considered mechanism.

The subject of future research will be determining the exact construction appearance of the machine components, as well as establishing a connection between the dimensions of the working space and mechanism parameters.

Verification of the future constructive design of the machine will again be realized by simulation in a virtual environment.

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